

ACINO

Application-Centric IP/optical
Network Orchestration

ACINO / D6.1

Project Website and Communication Kit

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This deliverable presents the ACINO project website and the communication kit.

Authors

Anders Gavler (ACREO)

Pontus Sköldström (ACREO)

Mikhail Popov (ACREO)

Domenico Siracusa (CREATE-NET)

Editor

Mikhail Popov (ACREO)

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Revision and history chart

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Summary

This deliverable presents a brief overview of the public ACINO webpage (available at: www.acino.eu) and provides a short description of the content of the web page. The objective of the project website is to promote the ACINO project and communicate about it to the rest of the world. It is also used as a collaborative space among the project members. The deliverable also provides information about the project twitter account (@acinoH2020) and the communication kit.

This document also communicates that the project website is up and running.

1 Project website structure

The ACINO project has an official website, which is available at: www.acino.eu. All project related information is available at the website; the main objective is to promote the ACINO project and to communicate about its progress to the outside world.

The front page is the main space of the website. The main content of the front page is summarized below:

- In the header, there is a first project description and the direct links to the twitter account and the contact email;
- The name of the project, its logo and the expansion of the acronym;
- A bar (navigation menu) connecting with the subpages listed in Table 1.1;
- A dynamic slider below explaining the challenge (first slide), the approach (second slide) and the solution (third slide);
- Three boxes to link to latest news, social network, next events
- Consortium logos

At the moment of writing the report, the front page of the website looked as shown in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: ACINO official website.

In order to produce the first version of the ACINO public website the work was carried out into two phases:

- **The initial phase:** it is focused on outlining major criteria for the public website such as: general outline, pages layout, menu/submenus, functionality, design, search engines etc.
- **The implementation phase:** it focused on the actual production and constant update of the public webpage. A unique domain **acino.eu** was purchased for that purpose. Then the webpage was built using WordPress¹ platform.

The website will be constantly improved and updated to provide good navigation experience to the users.

This section presents the outline of the ACINO website and briefly describes what pages it contains. The website has the pages listed in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1: ACINO website pages.

PAGES (Menu)	PAGES (Submenus)
About	Introduction to ACINO, Administrative, Objectives, Approach, Work breakdown, Impact
Outcomes	Deliverables, Publications, Tools and Events
Press	Page about latest news
Consortium	Page about the consortium
Meet us	Page about next events that will be attended by the consortium
Contact	Contact page
Login	Login for the internal project management tool

The navigation menu appears at the top of each page and makes it easy for visitors to find the information. Some of the items in the navigation menu have submenus which are visible when hovering over with a cursor.

The following sub-sections describe the pages listed in Table 1.1 more in details.

1.1 About

The page “**About**” is structured as follow:

- **Introduction to ACINO:** It provides a brief overview and basic information about the ACINO project.
- **Administrative:** It details the basic administrative facts.

¹ <https://wordpress.org/>

- **Objectives:** It presents the project's rationale, its objectives and structure using basic illustrations as support tools.
- **Approach:** It describes the ACINO approach.
- **Work breakdown:** It provides a description of the work divided into WPs.
- **Impact:** It provides an overview about the ACINO project expected impact.

1.2 Outcomes

The “**Outcomes**” webpage is dedicated to the results produced during the lifetime of the project, which includes:

- **Deliverables:** A list of deliverables produced by the project partners.
- **Publications:** A list of scientific publications submitted by the project partners.
- **Tools:** A list of tools and software used and developed by ACINO project consortium.
- **Events:** Various presentations regarding ACINO project in conference, seminars and project meetings.

There will be hyperlinks linked to each of the publications and deliverables available for public to read. This space will be progressively populated with the information.

1.3 Press

The page “**Press**” features the latest updates related to the project, press releases, pictures and articles and list of past and future events. There will be hyperlinks linked to each of the event, gallery and articles available for public to read. This space will be progressively populated with the information.

1.4 Consortium

The page “**Consortium**” lists partners participating in the projects with logos and links to their respective WebPages.

1.5 Meet us

The page “**Meet us**” lists the events organized by ACINO or where ACINO is going to participate. This space will be progressively populated with the information.

1.6 Contact

The page “**Contact**” provides contact information of the project coordinator for those who are interested to inquire about ACINO. There is also an optional fill-in form.

1.7 Login

The last tab in the menu bar is “**Login**” and it redirects to the internal Project Management Platform².

² <https://redmine.create-net.org/>

2 ACINO on the social networks

ACINO project is also active in social networks like Twitter, which ensure that updates or news related ACINO project are regularly updated to the social network space as well. The ACINO project account in twitter is available at: [@acinoH2020](https://twitter.com/acinoH2020). Figure 2.1 show the ACINO twitter channel.

Figure 2.1: ACINO Twitter channel.

The main objective of ACINO project twitter account is to disseminate the ACINO project activities to the followers, events and news like for example: project meetings, publications, demonstrations, etc. Additionally, consortium will follow similar projects in order to be aware about the activities of the different projects.

3 Project templates

As part of the communication kit, the templates for documents (e.g. deliverables) and for presentations have been uploaded in the internal project management platform². More specifically, two templates have been provided:

- Microsoft Word template (on which this report is based).
- Microsoft PowerPoint template (that has been used for D1.1 [4], as it is shown in Figure 3.1).

Approach

Application-centric: differentiate the service offered to each application all the way down to the optical layer

Figure 3.1: Example of Powerpoint template (taken from D1.1)

4 Project dissemination plan

A project dissemination plan has been created and uploaded to the internal project management platform², thus achieving the Milestone MS30 of the project [5], as reported in the DoW [6]. The project dissemination plan is a “living” list that includes the planned dissemination activities, such as submitted and published papers, presentation at workshops and conferences, workshop organizations, etc. It is meant to be a living document, constantly updated with the latest version. Figure 4.1 shows a screenshot as an example of the Project Dissemination Plan.

Date	End Date	Event Name/Title, Location	URL	Planned Participants	How will ACINO participate?	Targeted stakeholders
Planned Events 2015						
March						
22/03/2015	26/03/2015	Optical Fiber Communication conference (OFC), Los Angeles, USA	http://www.ofcconference.org/	ACINO WP6	General attendance, networking	Optical and data center network communities, testbeds
June						
29/06/2015	02/07/2015	European Conference on Networks and Communications, Paris, France	http://www.eucnc.eu/	ACINO WP6 (Specify)	General attendance, Workshop proposal sent	Optical and wireless network communities, EU projects, testbeds
September						
27/09/2015	01/10/2015	European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC), Valencia, Spain	http://www.ecoc2015.org/	ACINO WP6	General attendance, deadline regular papers - April 27, 2015	Optical network communities, testbeds
October						

Figure 4.1: Example Project Dissemination Plan.

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ACINO	Application-Centric IP/Optical Network Orchestation
DoW	Document of Work

References

- [1] ACINO Website: www.acino.eu
- [2] ACINO Intranet: <https://redmine.create-net.org/>
- [3] ACINO twitter account: [@acinoH2020](https://twitter.com/acinoH2020)
- [4] ACINO D1.1, “Public Project Presentation”.
- [5] ACINO MS30, “Dissemination Plan”.
- [6] ACINO Project Contract – Annex 1 “Description of the Work” (DoW).